

SPORT TOURISM MANAGEMENT MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE IN SICHUAN PROVINCE, CHINA

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Abstract

From the situation of sport tourism in China in recent years, the sport tourism has developed rapidly, but there are also many problems and shortcomings. The same is true for sport tourism in Sichuan Province, which is closely related to the sustainable management model of sport tourism. Therefore, in-depth research and exploration of its influencing factors are particularly important and crucial. So, I have conducted systematic research on this aspect. The purpose of this study is to: (1) to study the current situation and affecting factors of sport tourism management in Sichuan province, China. (2) To analyze factors positive effect sport tourism management model in Sichuan province, China. (3) To Examine and evaluate sport tourism management model in Sichuan province, China. This study adopted a mixed research method that combines quantitative and qualitative methods. Step 1: In the qualitative research section, expert was used to investigate the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable management models of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. Total of 10 participants. The tool used in this study is a structured interview. Step 2: In the quantitative research section, the sample consists of 500 respondents and is obtained through sampling. Use the method used to determine that the sample size is 20 times the inventory variable to calculate the sample size. Collect data using questionnaire survey method and analyze using structural equation modeling (SEM). Step 3: Through a combination of quantitative and qualitative research, 10 experts conducted focus group discussions and scoring. Experts have conducted evaluation of the feasibility, suitability, usefulness, and accuracy of the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. The research results indicate that: 1) the current situation the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province reflects the actual situation of the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. The sport tourism in Sichuan Province is constantly developing and progressing, and the number of sport tourism participants is gradually increasing. By comprehensively analyzing these factors, the sustainable management level of sport tourism in Sichuan Province can be further improved. 2) Government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior have a significant positive impact on the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. 3) Experts unanimously agree that the sport tourism management model for sustainable in Sichuan Province, China is Feasibility, Useful, Appropriate, Accuracy in A lot level-The most level. Therefore, this study helps to understand the overall status and influencing factors, sport tourism management model for sustainable in Sichuan Province, China, and to construct a development model, promote and apply it, laying a theoretical foundation for research related to sport tourism management model for sustainable in China.

Keywords: Sport Tourism, Sustainable Management Model, Government Policies and Support, Infrastructure Construction, Cultural and Historical Heritage Sites, Market Demand and Consumer Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of sustainable management models for sport tourism in Sichuan Province cannot be separated from many influencing factors, including government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior.

These factors are intertwined and jointly construct the development pattern of sustainable management models for sport tourism in Sichuan Province. Understanding these factors is crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the future development direction of sustainable management models for sport tourism in Sichuan Province.

At present, domestic and foreign researchers mainly focus on qualitative research on the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, while neglecting quantitative research on the factors that affect their development.

Therefore, in this study, the relationship between government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior and the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province was studied, and a model of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province was established.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Research on Government Policies and Support

Government policies and support refers to important measures to ensure people's livelihoods. The government formulates relevant policies to allocate social resources reasonably, promote social progress and improve people's livelihoods (Feng, 2024).

2.2 Research on Infrastructure Construction

Infrastructure construction refers to divide it into two types of infrastructure: material and institutional. Among them, material infrastructure includes conventional productive and non-productive facilities, while institutional infrastructure includes laws, political systems, policy regulations, etc. (Cao, 2023).

2.3 Research on Cultural and Historical Heritage Sites

Cultural and historical heritage sites refer to places with historical, cultural, artistic, technological, or natural significance, which possess precious physical and cultural heritage in the process of human civilization development (Chen, 2024).

Cultural and historical heritage sites refer to relic and relic of historical, artistic, and scientific value left over from human social activities. It is a precious historical and cultural heritage of humanity. It is a human cultural relic that remains in society or buried underground (Li, 2023).

2.4 Research on Market Demand and Consumer Behavior

Market demand and consumer behavior refers to the quantity of goods or services that a certain customer is willing and able to purchase in a certain region, time, marketing environment, and marketing plan (Meng, 2023). Market demand and consumer behavior refers to the process activities in which people seek, choose, purchase, use, evaluate, and dispose of products and services to meet their needs and desires, including subjective psychological activities and objective material activities of consumers(Lu ,2023).

2.5 Conceptual Framework

This study takes government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior as independent variables, and the dependent variable on the influencing factors of sustainable management models in sport tourism. Based on literature review and research objectives, a model of the influencing factors of sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province was constructed. The figure shows a schematic diagram of this model.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

This conceptual model provides the basic hypothetical relationship between the four factors of government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior and the influencing factors of sustainable management models in sport tourism. Assuming the following:

- H1: Government policies and support factor affect management model on sport tourism in Sichuan Province.
- H2: Infrastructure construction factor affect management model on sport tourism in Sichuan Province.
- H3: Cultural and historical heritage sites factor affect management model on sport tourism in Sichuan Province.
- H4: Market demand and consumer behavior factor affect management model on sport tourism in Sichuan Province.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The first step is for researchers to search for literature, books, theories, and related research on relevant professional disciplines both domestically and internationally. Collect data through interviews and use purposeful random sampling to select the target sample group, in order to understand and summarize the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable management of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China. The second step is to use the Chinese online questionnaire platform for data collection. Then use SmartPLS4 to analyze the collected questionnaire data, establish a structural equation model, and validate four hypotheses. The third step is focus group discussion. Through group discussions and expert discussions on opinions and information, the collected interview data related to the factors affecting the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China will be for qualitative research. Using the sustainability evaluation table of factors influencing the sustainable model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, analyze the information in the focus group discussion through content analysis and quantitative research. Evaluate the feasibility, applicability, effectiveness, and accuracy of the sustainable management model for sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Research on the influencing factors the sustainable business models of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China. This article adopts a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods.

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

This section studies the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable management of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China. The following is an interview summary:

This study investigates the current situation of factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. It is found that China has adopted various methods

to ensure the sustainable management of sport tourism, aiming to enhance the overall strength and industry competitiveness of sport tourism. Sichuan Province has taken a series of effective measures in the management and construction of sport tourism, aiming to optimize the business environment, management and development mechanism of sport tourism, thereby improving the overall level of sport tourism in Sichuan Province and cultivating sport tourism with outstanding abilities in the current fierce competition. To improve the sustainable management level of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, it is necessary to start from the foundation and work together from multiple aspects. After research, it has been summarized that there are four factors that affect the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province: government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior.

4.2 Quantitative Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed in this study. This study organized and analyzed the basic information of the respondents, and described the overall distribution of the sample from seven aspects: gender, age, education background, nature of work, working seniority, place of residence, Average monthly income.

4.2.2 Reliability and Validity Analysis

Table 1: First-order Construct Reliability Test Results Table

Variable	Number of measurement items	Cronbach's alpha
Amusement_facilities	4	0.854
Communication_facilities	4	0.874
Consumer_satisfaction	4	0.861
Cultural Experience_Projects	4	0.866
Cultural Heritage_Activities	4	0.869
Diversity_of_tourist demand	4	0.857
Economic growth	4	0.867
Effectiveness_of_online marketing	4	0.868
Financial_allocations	4	0.855
Infrastructure_investment	4	0.866
Maintenance_prevention	4	0.854
Market_competitiveness	4	0.864
Marketing_and publicity	4	0.873
Participation_satisfaction	4	0.867
Protection_of_Historical Sites	4	0.881
Regulatory_and_policy environment	4	0.863
Seasonal_demand changes	4	0.867
Social influence	4	0.864
Tourist Interest_in Culture	4	0.866
Traffic_network	4	0.866
Venue facilities	4	0.867

This study uses Cronbach's Alpha to test the reliability of the research structure and dimensions of the sample. As can be seen from the table, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of the main structures and dimensions involved in this study are all greater than 0.7, reaching the corresponding judgment standard, so the scale reliability of the sample is relatively high.

4.2.3 Validity Analysis

Table 2: Validation Factor AVE and CR Index Values

Variable	CR	AVE
Amusement_facilities	0.901	0.695
Communication_facilities	0.913	0.725
Consumer_satisfaction	0.905	0.705
Cultural Experience_Projects	0.908	0.713
Cultural Heritage_Activities	0.91	0.718
Diversity_of_tourist demand	0.903	0.7
Economic growth	0.91	0.716
Effectiveness_of_online marketing	0.91	0.717
Financial_allocations	0.902	0.697
Infrastructure_investment	0.908	0.713
Maintenance_prevention	0.901	0.696
Market_competitiveness	0.908	0.711
Marketing_and publicity	0.913	0.724
Participation_satisfaction	0.909	0.715
Protection_of_Historical Sites	0.918	0.738
Regulatory_and_policy environment	0.907	0.709
Seasonal_demand changes	0.91	0.716
Social influence	0.907	0.71
Tourist Interest_in Culture	0.909	0.713
Traffic_network	0.909	0.714
Venue facilities	0.909	0.715

The relevant parameters for the convergence validity analysis of Sport tourism management model for sustainable in Sichuan Province, China are shown in the table above. From the table, it can be seen that the AVE values of all factors are greater than 0.50, the CR values of all factors are greater than 0.70, indicating that the latent variable has good convergent validity; All fitting indices meet the standard.

The confirmatory factor analysis of this structural model shows that the fit between the model and the data is good, and the model has good explanatory and predictive power. This indicates that the model has a good fitting effect. Therefore, from the perspective of confirmatory factor analysis, it is believed that the validity of the Sport tourism management model for sustainable in Sichuan Province, China scale is better.

4.2.4 Structural Equation Model

This study used SmartPLS4.0 to establish a path model and imported the collected 500 sample data into it. The path model estimation diagram is shown in Figure.

Figure 2: Research Path Model Diagram

Table 3: HTMT Criterion Checklist for Indicator Variables in Measurement Models

	IAF	ICF	MCS	CCP	CCA	MDD	SEG	MEM	GFA	GII	IMP	MMC	GMP	SPE	CPS	GRE	MSC	SSI	CTC	ITN	IVF	
IAF																						
ICF	0.58																					
MCS	0.325	0.425																				
CCP	0.422	0.42	0.421																			
CCA	0.407	0.386	0.394	0.538																		
MDD	0.374	0.444	0.522	0.443	0.369																	
SEG	0.417	0.469	0.404	0.423	0.387	0.427																
MEM	0.313	0.455	0.557	0.416	0.368	0.587	0.378															
GFA	0.424	0.424	0.377	0.46	0.387	0.32	0.393	0.39														
GII	0.441	0.394	0.424	0.484	0.352	0.412	0.431	0.371	0.543													
IMP	0.587	0.58	0.399	0.425	0.419	0.417	0.444	0.394	0.419	0.436												
MMC	0.405	0.466	0.592	0.469	0.427	0.586	0.449	0.556	0.446	0.426	0.486											
GMP	0.425	0.43	0.388	0.463	0.473	0.362	0.398	0.382	0.557	0.577	0.425	0.38										
SPE	0.399	0.382	0.35	0.381	0.364	0.32	0.537	0.379	0.421	0.352	0.42	0.424	0.342									
CPS	0.429	0.431	0.398	0.608	0.528	0.428	0.443	0.44	0.382	0.402	0.404	0.431	0.404	0.414								
GRE	0.473	0.467	0.47	0.469	0.428	0.457	0.429	0.441	0.608	0.612	0.459	0.476	0.589	0.404	0.428							
MSC	0.325	0.439	0.536	0.424	0.356	0.559	0.357	0.568	0.389	0.399	0.385	0.591	0.4	0.377	0.451	0.486						
SSI	0.414	0.413	0.416	0.416	0.404	0.405	0.548	0.381	0.45	0.386	0.442	0.457	0.439	0.536	0.423	0.486	0.421					
CTC	0.348	0.407	0.374	0.582	0.582	0.398	0.411	0.368	0.414	0.404	0.374	0.413	0.487	0.352	0.571	0.438	0.366	0.393				
ITN	0.571	0.611	0.363	0.457	0.393	0.411	0.379	0.416	0.402	0.399	0.578	0.474	0.388	0.356	0.461	0.45	0.401	0.379	0.388			
IVF	0.602	0.623	0.429	0.438	0.358	0.397	0.464	0.425	0.489	0.506	0.654	0.433	0.468	0.428	0.427	0.452	0.439	0.427	0.387	0.607		

According to the data in Table, the HTMT ratio of most indicator variables is less than 1. According to the HTMT criteria, this indicates that the average correlation between different latent variables is much lower than the average correlation between internal indicators of the same latent variable.

Therefore, it can be concluded that there are significant differences among the latent variables, that is, they represent different latent constructs, and their discriminant validity is good.

Table 4: Variable Interpretation Rate

	R-square	R-square adjusted	Result
CCA	0.587	0.587	Relatively strong
CCP	0.632	0.631	Relatively strong
CPS	0.635	0.634	Relatively strong
CTC	0.632	0.632	Relatively strong
GFA	0.601	0.6	Relatively strong
GII	0.622	0.621	Relatively strong
GMP	0.623	0.622	Relatively strong
GRE	0.663	0.662	Relatively strong
IAF	0.582	0.581	Relatively strong
ICF	0.623	0.622	Relatively strong
IMP	0.609	0.609	Relatively strong
ITN	0.603	0.602	Relatively strong
IVF	0.655	0.654	Relatively strong
MCS	0.591	0.59	Relatively strong
MDD	0.582	0.581	Relatively strong
MEM	0.596	0.596	Relatively strong
MMC	0.62	0.619	Relatively strong
MSC	0.566	0.566	Relatively strong
SE	0.452	0.548	Relatively strong
SEG	0.652	0.652	Relatively strong
SPE	0.636	0.635	Relatively strong
SSI	0.649	0.649	Relatively strong

The calculation results show that the predictive explanatory rate of the four independent variables of government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior in the model on the influencing factors of sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province is 0.548, higher than 0.330, belonging to the level of moderate or above explanatory level.

Table 5: Variable Prediction Determination Coefficient

	F-square	Result
Government policies and support	0.035	High
Infrastructure construction	0.033	High
Cultural and historical heritage sites	0.05	High
Market demand and consumer behavior	0.039	High

The calculation results show that the predictive coefficients of the four variables: Government policies and support, Infrastructure construction, Cultural and historical heritage sites, Market demand and consumer behavior for the dependent variable are all higher than 0.02, indicating that the predictive performance of the model is good.

Table 6: Predicted Correlation Scores

	SSO	Residual Sum of Squares (SSE)	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	Result
CCA	220	1059.959	0.518	High
CCP	2200	1076.451	0.511	High
CPS	2200	991.289	0.549	High
CTC	2200	1074.59	0.512	High
GFA	2200	1132.019	0.485	High
GII	2200	1075.536	0.511	High
GMP	2200	1037.856	0.528	High
GRE	2200	1088.227	0.505	High
IAF	2200	1138.513	0.482	High
ICF	2200	1031.915	0.531	High
IMP	2200	1134.932	0.484	High
ITN	2200	1072.189	0.513	High
IVF	2200	1067.357	0.515	High
MCS	2200	1064.868	0.516	High
MDD	2200	1122.937	0.49	High
MEM	2200	1061.288	0.518	High
MMC	2200	1081.933	0.508	High
MSC	2200	1102.344	0.499	High
SE	6600	4157.054	0.37	High
SEG	2200	1063.866	0.516	High
SPE	2200	1070.025	0.514	High
SSI	2200	1084.903	0.507	High

In the structural model, Q² represents the predicted correlation of variables, and the larger the value, the stronger the predicted correlation. The calculation results show that the Q² statistical correlation between the variables and the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China is 0.37 indicating that the selected government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior have a high predictive effect on the dependent variable of the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China.

4.2.5 Structural Model Path Coefficients/Relationships

Table 7: Hypothesis Testing

Assumption	Path relationship	path coefficient	T	P value	Decide
Assumption	Government policies and support -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China	0.189	4.213	0	Supported
Assumption	Infrastructure construction -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China	0.189	3.907	0	Supported
Assumption	Cultural and historical heritage sites -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China	0.23	4.707	0	Supported
Assumption	Market demand and consumer behavior -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China	0.2	4.615	0	Supported

It will test and validate the research hypotheses proposed in this article, in this study, the path coefficients of the PLS algorithm in Smart pls 4.0 were used to measure the impact. If the path coefficient is greater than 0, it indicates a positive impact. A path coefficient less than 0 indicates a negative impact. The size of the path coefficient represents the magnitude of the impact. Meanwhile, the t-value must be greater than the critical value, and the P-value must be less than the critical value to confirm significance.

The direct effect test is shown in the table: Government policies and support has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China ($\beta = 0.189$, $t = 4.213 > 1.96$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$), assuming H1 is validated. Infrastructure construction has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China ($\beta = 0.189$, $T = 3.907 > 1.96$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$), assuming H2 is validated.

Assuming H3 is validated, Cultural and historical heritage sites significantly positively affects the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China ($\beta = 0.230$, $T = 4.707 > 1.96$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$). The Market demand and consumer behavior has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China ($\beta = 0.200$, $T = 4.615 > 1.96$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$), H4 was validated.

4.3 Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis

This stage aims to examine and evaluate the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. The qualitative research section of this study used interview methods to select respondents for investigation, organized interview data, and analyzed the data. A quantitative study is conducted to evaluate the feasibility, practicality, suitability, and accuracy of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province using the sustainability evaluation table of the influencing factors of the sustainable development model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province.

4.3.1 Research Result

Research has found that the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, as a core category of development direction, can connect and explain the correlation between various categories. Therefore, the researchers constructed a theoretical model of the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, with government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior as the core. Expert's unanimous agree that the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan province, China. Is Feasibility, Useful, Appropriate, Accuracy.in A lot level-The most level. Be seen that the above content is an important influencing factor for the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

In the development process of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, the four factors of government policies and support, infrastructure construction, cultural and historical heritage sites, market demand and consumer behavior have a significant positive impact on the development of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. The results of this study confirm that the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province are closely related to their four components. Therefore, this study helps to use structural equation modeling to measure the factors influencing the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province in various ways. Among the factors that affect the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, the better ones can promote the development of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, and have a greater impact on the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, thereby promoting the development of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China.

5.2 Discussion

5.2.1 It was found that in the path analysis of government policies and support, the influencing factors of sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province were explored. The P-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, and the standard path coefficient is 0.189, indicating that

government policies and support has a significant impact on the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China. Corresponds to wang (2023) found in "Textual Analysis of my country's Sports Tourism Policy from the Perspective of Policy Tools" that sports tourism policy is the top-level design to promote the development of sports tourism, and sports tourism policy tools are the means and ways to effectively solve the problems that restrict sports tourism development planning.

5.2.2 It was found that in the path analysis of the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province was explored. The P-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, and the standard path coefficient is 0.189, indicating that infrastructure construction has a significant impact on the sustainable management model of Sichuan Province, China. Corresponds to xue (2020) found in "A Brief Discussion on the Planning Strategy of Sports Tourism Infrastructure in Wuhai City" that equipment and equipment sufficient and good quality equipment and equipment to ensure that tourists can carry out sports activities safely and comfortably, enhance the tourism experience.

5.2.3 It was found that in the path analysis of the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province was explored. The P-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, and the standard path coefficient is 0.189, indicating that infrastructure construction has a significant impact on the sustainable management model of Sichuan Province, China. Corresponds to yi (2016)"Research on Quan Culture, Sports and Tourism Resources and Market Development in Jinan City" Research results: The spring water resources and profound spring culture in Jinan, as well as economic, political, transportation, geographical location and other factors, make the development of spring culture sport tourism resources and markets feasible.

5.2.4 It was found that in the path analysis, Market demand and consumer behavior has been studied on the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. The P-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that innovative marketing has a significant impact on the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province. Corresponds to deng (2022)"Research on the Current Situation and Market Management Model of Ethnic Minority sport tourism in Guangxi". Research findings: To promote the integration and upgrading of ethnic sport tourism industry from the integration of ethnic sports products, ethnic sport tourism industry, destination tourism image, independence of tourism enterprises, and development of ethnic sports creative cultural industry.

5.3 Suggestion

Strengthen government policies and support, strengthen infrastructure construction, strengthening the protection of cultural and historical heritage, strengthen innovative marketing capabilities. The purpose of this study is to explore in depth the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of sport tourism in Sichuan Province, China. Subsequent researchers will also attempt to conduct relevant research on the influencing factors of sustainable management models of sport tourism in other countries and regions, and will compare and analyze the results of this study to expand the external validity of the research.

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